

(SHORT COMMUNICATION)

Net-zero catastrophe beginning?

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Abstract

Historically, warm eras such as the Minoan Warm Period, the Roman Warm Period, and the Medieval Warm Period were all eras where there was very little volcanic activity, with the result that their atmospheres were normally free of dimming volcanic SO₂ aerosol emissions, This allowed world-wide temperatures to rise 2 to 4 degrees above current temperatures, causing droughts, famines, and the demise of earlier cultures around the world.

Current Net-Zero activities banning the burning of fossil fuels and their SO₂ aerosol emissions will have the unintended consequence of causing temperatures to rise to those of the earlier eras.

Keywords: Climate Change; Net Zero; SO₂ aerosols; CO₂

1. Introduction

Net-Zero will be a Climate Catastrophe of our own making!

Its object is the elimination of the burning of fossil fuels because of their release of additional CO₂ into the atmosphere, where its increase is hypothesized to lead to Catastrophic Anthropogenic Global Warming, if not curtailed.

However, their burning also releases Sulfur Dioxide (SO₂) aerosols (a fine mist of Sulfuric Acid) into the atmosphere. SO₂ aerosols are reflective, and cool the planet by decreasing the intensity of the Sun's rays striking its surface. VEI4 and larger volcanic eruptions also insert SO₂ aerosols into the stratosphere, where they have the same dimming effect.

Global Industrial SO₂ aerosol emissions peaked at 136 Megatons in 1979, and due primarily to American and European "Clean Air" efforts, they fell to 79 Megatons by 2019 (latest source data available). Their decrease is the actual cause of the increased warming since circa 1980, since average anomalous global temperatures ALWAYS rise whenever global SO₂ aerosols levels decrease. Rising CO₂ levels have no detectable climatic effect beyond that of decreased SO₂ aerosols and thus are of no climatic concern.

Historically, warming due to the near absence of SO₂ aerosols in the atmosphere occurred during the Medieval Warm Period (MWP), circa 950-1250 AD, as well as during the Roman Warm Period (RWP), 250 BC-450 AD, and the Minoan Warm Period (3500-1100 BC).

For the 300-year world-wide MWP, there were only 31 VEI4 and higher eruptions (about 10 per century), so that most of the time Earth's atmosphere was free of protective SO₂ aerosols. Glaciers melted, Greenland was farmed, droughts, famines, and high temperatures destroyed earlier cultures, such as those in Central America, and the American South West.

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For the 650-year world-wide RWP, 77 such eruptions are recorded, about 8 per century, with just 11 larger than VEI4. As with the MWP, temperatures then were about 2 Deg. C. higher than today.

For the 2,400-year Minoan Warm Period, there are only 114 eruptions recorded, about 5 per century. Temperatures were about 4 Deg. C. higher than today, the weather was stormy, and the Minoan Civilization reportedly collapsed because of a long period of elevated temperatures.,

By ways of comparison, there were 144 eruptions during the Little Ice Age (LIA), approx. 1250-1850, 24 per century, with 38 larger than VEI4. All LIA temperature decreases coincide with volcanic eruptions and their SO₂ aerosol emissions.

There were 48 eruptions in the 19th century, and 78 in the 20th the century, each exceeding or matching the totals for the earlier 300-year and 600-year periods. Clearly, Earth's atmosphere was far more transparent during the other warm periods.

Although volcanic SO₂ aerosols temporarily cool our planet, the millions of tons of Industrial aerosols currently in our atmosphere provide far more cooling than that from volcanoes, where the average emission for VEI4 eruptions is 0.2 million tons. Their removal by Net-Zero activities will quickly cause temperatures to rise to those of the earlier warm periods, or perhaps even higher, because of Earth's larger population.

2. Conclusion

Trillions of dollars are being spent around the world to implement Net Zero, whose end result will be to bring about the Catastrophic Global warming that it is trying too avid. To prevent this inevitable catastrophe, all Net-Zero efforts should be halted as quickly as possible. We may already be near a tipping point of increasing weather variability, with scorching temperatures in 2022 in California, the South West, Great Britain, India, Pakistan, and elsewhere around the globe, as well as disastrous floodings,, even though we have been in a cool La Nina state since late 2020.

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